

The pineal gland, a global review of its functions and its relationship with spiritual practices

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ABSTRACT

The pineal gland, often called the "third eye" in spiritual traditions, is considered a bridge between the physical and spiritual worlds. Located in the center of the brain, it produces melatonin, a hormone that regulates sleep-wake cycles and influences circadian rhythms. In spiritual practices such as meditation, the pineal gland is often associated with intuition, mental clarity and spiritual awakening. Meditators seek to activate or "open" this gland to achieve heightened states of consciousness, favoring mystical experiences, a deeper connection to the universe and heightened intuitive understanding. Meditation, visualization and breathing practices can stimulate the pineal gland, potentially increasing melatonin production and thus altering states of consciousness to facilitate spiritual and introspective experiences. The link between the pineal gland and spiritual practices such as meditation lies in the characteristics of the different hormones secreted by this gland. Melatonin and Dimethyltryptamine are both useful when the body shifts from consciousness to a state of unconsciousness, notably sleep. The study of all states of consciousness then becomes the next stage of research, notably states of consciousness that tend towards unconsciousness, or sleep.

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1 Introduction

The main aim of this review is to compile and synthesize the global knowledge we have about the pineal gland and its functions, without delving into rare and exceptional cases or discussing the latest unpublished but still uncertain discoveries. The second aim of this article is to highlight the links between the pineal gland and the various energetic functions of the human body, particularly in the context of proven spiritual practices such as meditation.

This review adds value by bringing together a set of unrelated data and suggesting a relationship between them, which remains to be studied experimentally. The pineal gland, also known as the epiphysis, is a small endocrine gland located in the center of the brain. It has attracted significant interest not only for its biological functions but also for its supposed link with spiritual and mystical

practices throughout the ages. In this review, we examine the reasons why this gland is thought to have a link with spirituality.

2 Pineal Gland

2.1 Description

The pineal gland has been the subject of considerable interest from researchers for decades. The study (Scientific Research On The Pineal Gland: A Bibliometric Analysis From Its First Publication, n. d.) shows that the literature review revealed a total of 8719 publications on the subject of the pineal gland. The most productive author was Reiter, Russel J., while the most productive institute was the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique in France.

The first detailed description of the pineal gland was given by Galen in his work "De anatomicis administrationibus".

The pineal gland is a small neuroendocrine gland located in the midline of the skull and forms part of the epithalamus and hypothalamus, regulating their secretion. It is made up of pinealocytes, glial cells, interstitial cells, perivascular phagocytes, and sometimes calcified aggregates. It is the pinealocytes that make this organ highly vascularized, with permeable capillaries. This organ therefore contains neural tissue, as it requires neuroendocrine connections. Its size diminishes at puberty.

It measures $5 \times 10 \times 8$ millimeters and weighs 120 milligrams, its weight varying according to the season (Al-Suhaimi and Khan 2022). Furthermore, Singh et al. (2023), based on pineal gland samples, assert that the number of pinealocytes decreases with age, while the size of calcified aggregates increases with age. Some of the authors who publish on the subject are convinced that it plays a vital role in spiritual functions. This idea originated with René Descartes, who asserted that the Pineal Gland was the link between body and soul.

Culturally, it is referred to as the human being's "third eye", being a gland sensitive to light. It is also defined as the sixth of the seven major chakras of Hindu Tantrism, named "Ajna", which represents the chakra of intuition and knowledge.

The pineal gland secretes various hormones essential for the maintenance of body and mind functions of varying importance. The most important of these is melatonin. Through the production of melatonin and the regulation of circadian rhythms, the pineal gland plays a central role in maintaining homeostatic functions. It influences sleep, body temperature, the immune system, reproductive functions, and mood. Proper functioning of the pineal gland is therefore crucial to physiological balance and overall well-being.

2.2 Melatonin

Melatonin, mainly synthesized by the pineal gland and the hypothalamus, is a neurohormone which is synthesized from a neurotransmitter (serotonin) which is itself synthesized from the amino acid tryptophan. It is mainly synthesized at night, and its role is to facilitate sleep induction.

Melatonin's main physiological function is to transmit information about the daily day-night cycle to the body's systems, in order to organize functions that respond to alterations in photoperiod.

Its secretion levels fluctuate significantly during the night, depending on the phase of the sleep cycle. Its proportions are more likely to be influenced by exogenous factors in our immediate environment than by functions such as activity, sleep, rest, meals and physical effort. We know, for example, that exposure to blue light significantly reduces melatonin secretion, while exposure to red light seems to have the opposite effect. Some studies show that the amount of melatonin released in the body is proportional to the volume

of the pineal gland. This knowledge makes it easier to determine the role of this gland in homeostatic functions.

Melatonin regulates and organizes circadian rhythms. It can be designated as a "circadian phase marker" in various biomaterials such as plasma or saliva (Skene and Arendt 2006). It is an endocrine output signal of the biological clock and provides circadian information as an endogenous synchronizer, stabilizing and reinforcing circadian rhythms.

Moreover, these receptors are located widely in organs, making the putative therapeutic indications for this hormone diverse (Smolensky et al. 2016). It can act as an anti-inflammatory and antioxidant agent, and play a role in glucose and lipid homeostasis and DNA repair mechanisms. Melatonin also prevents memory impairment induced by consumption of a high-fat diet (HFD) in rats, by preventing oxidative stress changes in the hippocampus of the brain.

In the journal ("Exploring The Role Of Melatonin In Meditation On Cardiovascular Health", 2022) we establish the relationship between meditation and the role of melatonin in cardiovascular protection.

Accumulating evidence also indicates that melatonin and its metabolites can slow neurodegenerative processes and show protective effects against stress (Bob & Fedor-Freybergh, 2007). The work by Al-Suhaimi and Khan (2022) entitled "Adrenal Glands, Pineal Gland, and the Circadian Rhythm: Structure and Physiology" lists and summarizes the main characteristics of melatonin, which can be found scattered throughout the literature. We'll be focusing on aspects that are relevant to our review objectives.

2.3 Pinoline

Pinoline is also synthesized in the pineal gland, as part of the melatonin metabolism process.

This molecule has remarkable biological properties, notably as an antioxidant. One of these pharmacological properties is its ability to promote neurogenesis in vitro, even at very low levels. Both pinoline and melatonin have been shown to reduce lipid peroxidation. Lipid peroxidation is a deleterious process that leads to cell membrane degradation and neuronal dysfunction. The study by Aranda et al (2010), for example, demonstrates its efficacy against oxidative damage and membrane rigidity in the liver.

Pinoline's potential therefore seems vast, with capacities that could be involved in neuronal regeneration processes and brain plasticity.

2.4 Di-méthyl-tryptamine (DMT)

N,N-di-methyl-tryptamine (DMT) is a psychedelic compound identified as endogenous in mammals. "N-N" refers to two nitrogen atoms; "dimethyl" refers to two CH₃ groups replacing H. There are various enzymes required for the synthesis of di-methyl-tryptamine in the pineal gland, including aromatic L-amino acid decarboxylase (AADC)

and indolethylamine-N-methyltransferase (INMT). Its natural synthesis generally occurs during dreams and death. The study by Dean et al. (2019) shows a significant increase in DMT levels in the rat visual cortex after the induction of experimental cardiac arrest, suggesting the possibility that this phenomenon may occur similarly in human brains. This study highlights important potential implications for the understanding of consciousness and spirituality, such as the possibility that DMT plays a role in the near-death experience phenomenon.

Administered and not naturally synthesized DMT is reputed to be used for its psychedelic effects, resulting in a deep, immersive sense of physical transcendence, as well as rich, vivid auditory distortions and visual images. The study by Pasquini et al. (2024) demonstrates, using simultaneous fMRI and ECG signals, that IV administration of DMT induces hyperactivity in the superior temporal lobe, as well as deactivations in the hippocampus and medial parietal cortex. At the same time, there is growing interest in the medical use of DMT, as various studies using it to influence psychiatric disorders have shown positive results. The review by Brecksema et al. (2020) explains that the use of psychedelics in the treatment of mental disorders is not sufficiently understood. Despite this, its use in a controlled environment has shown significant results, not least according to similar therapeutic processes which lead to comparable results.

2.5 Calcification

Pineal gland calcification refers to the deposition of calcium salts (mainly in the form of hydroxyapatite) within the pineal gland. This process is visible on X-rays and CT scans, where the gland appears as a small white spot. There are several reasons for calcification, the main cause of pineal calcification is aging. As we age, calcium metabolism changes and calcium deposits can accumulate in various body tissues.

The Retinoschisin (RS1) plays a key role in pineal gland calcification (PGC) in mice through both extracellular and intracellular pathways. RS1 was clustered around the cell membrane or intracellularly in pinealocytes, actively participating in the exchange of calcium and thereby mediating PGC. Liu et al. (2024).

The review by Liu and Liu (2023) brings together numerous studies to show that the complex phenomenon of pineal gland calcification affects melatonin secretion and release, leading to a direct imbalance in the central nervous system. Its calcification affects its normal functions, which can have a major impact on biological and physiological processes, including the regulation of sleep, the immune system, and certain mental functions.

2.6 Influence

We've taken a closer look at the different hormones secreted by the pineal gland. These different hormones are of crucial importance for various organisms in the body, notably by influencing other glands, especially the pituitary, endocrine pancreas, adrenal glands, parathyroid glands and gonads.

3 Circadian mechanisms

The term circadian comes from its Latin etymology "circa diem", meaning "almost a day".

The circadian rhythm belongs to a scientific discipline known as chronobiology. Chronobiology refers to the study of temporal biological rhythms. It may involve the study of endogenous biological rhythms within the organism, or exogenous rhythms specific to the environment.

The pineal gland is responsible for regulating and maintaining circadian rhythms. By regulating the release of melatonin, pinoline and di-methyl-tryptamine, it plays a role in modulating the brain's states of consciousness. Many factors are involved in modulating these states of consciousness. The pineal gland is guided by exogenous factors such as the transition between light and darkness of the sun's natural cycles, which represent the main Zeitgeber.

It is the only gland that is sensitive to light. It is therefore essential to maintain a normal circadian rhythm of sleep-wake cycles, without which the human being is no longer able to live properly.

Abnormalities in circadian rhythms observed in patients in the minimally conscious state (MCS) and vegetative state (UWS) could serve as markers to differentiate between different disorders of consciousness (DOC) at diagnosis (Raciti et al., 2023).

McClung's (2007) work explores the different ways in which circadian rhythms can influence mood and behavior in people with bipolar disorder. It highlights the underlying biological mechanisms, including the impact of circadian clock genes. Various studies demonstrate the impact of circadian desynchronization on vulnerability to manic and depressive episodes in bipolar disorder.

However, it seems that lithium, a common treatment for bipolar disorder, can stabilize circadian rhythms by having a direct impact on the genes that regulate circadian clocks. It influences the expression of genes such as CLOCK and BMAL1 and increases the amplitude of circadian oscillations, which means it enhances the regularity and predictability of biological cycles.

4 Oneiric functions

4.1 Dreams

Humans spend around a third of their lives asleep. Sleep, a phase of regeneration and rest, comprises 5 cycles, including light sleep, deep sleep and REM sleep. It is during this last phase of REM sleep, also known as REM (Rapid Eye Movement), that humans are subject to the phenomenon of dreaming (Maurizi, 1985).

Everyone dreams, and we can dream about anything. Dreaming holds the key to most of the human sciences, and

despite the fact that its mechanisms have never really been studied,

Callaway's (1988) article offers a sketch of one of the mechanisms of dreaming through a metabolic dream cycle, and postulates that such a mechanism may be distinct from the physiological symptomatology seen in the rapid eye movements of REMS. With tryptamines and beta-carbolines proposed as research targets, it may eventually become possible to find "the stuff dreams are made of".

According to recent measurements, higher levels of melatonin in the blood induce more intense and emotionally salient dreams than a placebo control.

4.2 Hallucination

It is possible to establish a relationship, based on existing literature, between various parts of the hallucinatory spectrum and the functions of the pineal gland. However, this aspect of the link is hardly well-founded and lacking in experimentation. Barker's (2018) work published in *Frontiers in Neuroscience* discusses the potential presence of DMT in the pineal gland. Research shows that DMT could be produced by the pineal gland could play a role in altered states of consciousness, including hallucinations and near-death experiences. The authors stress the need for further research to determine the distribution and concentration of DMT in the brain, and how it might affect various neuronal receptors.

It is clear that minute concentrations of N,N-dimethyltryptamine have been detected in the brain, but these are not sufficient to produce psychoactive effects. Alternative explanations are presented for how stress and imminent death can produce altered states of consciousness without invoking the intermediary of N,N-dimethyltryptamine. However, we know that the pineal gland plays a role in hallucinatory and delusional phenomena that may be associated with schizophrenic delusions or alcohol withdrawal states. Elevated levels of melatonin and vasotocin in the cerebrospinal fluid, normally present during REM sleep, are thought to be present during the waking period, inducing delusional perception.

4.3 Meditation

A large body of evidence now demonstrates the link between the practice of meditation and the development of the pineal gland. This is evidenced mainly by a higher fMRI MRI signal in the pineal gland of meditators, and a higher level of melatonin than in controls.

Meditation and mindfulness practices have their roots not only in psychology, but also in neuroscience and neurobiology. They manifest themselves in the brain through both functional and structural changes in gray and white matter. These changes are notably located in the regions and networks involved in attention, memory, interoception and sensory processing, as well as in self-regulation and self-management mechanisms.

Some studies have used live magnetic resonance imaging during a meditation session. The Department of Neurology at the University of Taiwan observed the whole brain during the practice of a classical form of meditation known as "quiet sitting". Their work showed positive activation of the pineal gland and hypothalamus during the first and second stages of this meditation. Changes in the BOLD (Blood Oxygenation Level Dependent) signal were also observed (Liou et al., 2005).

4.4 Why study meditation?

For the next studies we'll look at, we're talking about the practice of mindfulness meditation, which is generally the one most often used in experimental measurement protocols for its ease of implementation and speed of results.

According to the study by Plini et al (2024), (long-term) meditation practice promotes pineal gland integrity and suggests that it may have a beneficial effect on brain ageing, based on BrainPAD scores being used to estimate brain age.

This could be explained by the role of hormonal metabolism in the maintenance of gray matter, in particular, melatonin's roles in sleep, immune response, modulation of inflammation and regeneration of stem cells and neurons.

It should not be forgotten, however, that the various forms of meditation demonstrate a lasting change on the brain or on behavior only after relatively long periods of practice. The study by Rajan and Singh (2023), for example, raises questions about the effectiveness of portable biofeedback devices in meditation practice. This leads to the conclusion that it is important to monitor and carry out measurements rigorously and correctly targeted to meditation subjects, especially if the studies are conducted over the short or medium term. The notion of the long term often comes up in meditation practice.

Apart from this, the positive effects of meditation are wide-ranging and increasingly demonstrated in the scientific literature.

The study by Hölzel et al (2011) used magnetic resonance imaging to show that the practice of mindfulness increases grey matter density in brain regions linked to learning and memory, emotional regulation, and the processing of perspectives of self and others.

The study by Hooper et al (2024) on a population of young women shows that 10 minutes of meditation a day can significantly improve self-esteem, body appreciation and mood. Also, the study by Lee et al (2024) on a population of young men shows that introducing mediation into a routine reduces depression, perceived stress and anxiety, and increases self-esteem. This is easily explained on the basis of elementary psychological models. Indeed, an overly elaborate and inflexible conceptualization of the self plays a particularly important etiological role in psychopathology (Hayes et al., 2006). Various forms of meditation help to

alleviate suffering and resistance, by loosening the bonds with a rigid self-concept.

The work of Khatib et al (2023) measures the effects of meditation on pain perception, demonstrating that it directly and significantly reduces chronic pain. Meanwhile, the study by Módis et al (2024) suggests that spirituality may play a significant role in modulating immune responses and disease activity. The possibility of psychosomatic mechanisms of action needs to be studied in greater depth.

It has been shown that chronic stress throughout life leads to degeneration in certain parts of the prefrontal cortex (PFC), resulting, among other things, in a reduced ability to regulate emotions, but also a deterioration in executive functions and a reduction in working memory performance in the dorsolateral PFC.

4.5 Link between meditation and pineal gland

When meditation is practiced, melatonin is secreted, and this is what enables a modification of the state of consciousness. Altered consciousness opens up vast fields of study, requiring a deeper understanding of nocturnal mechanisms. It is during sleep that the body regenerates and carries out all the operations required to regulate the various somatic disorders and recover from the difficulties encountered in the conscious state.

We have also seen that the state of meditation as a whole activates regenerative functions, which may be psychic or purely somatic. We therefore understand that regenerative processes take place in altered states of consciousness. Other types of process can be exercised during altered states of consciousness, such as cognitive or neuro-linguistic programming during hypnosis sessions, for example.

5 States of consciousness

Consciousness is a multi-faceted concept, involving both wakefulness, i.e. a state of alertness regulated by the brain stem, and awareness, a subjective experience of any thought, perception or emotion. altered state of consciousness

States of consciousness correspond to the level of wakefulness and the level of awareness available in an individual's state. They are measured by brain frequencies, which are the undulating result of neuronal electrical activity. They are classified according to the Greek alphabet (Gamma, Beta, Alpha, Theta and Delta), where Gamma corresponds to the state of maximum alertness and perception.

In deeply altered states of consciousness such as sleep (Delta), self-monitoring and self-observation of regenerative processes is extremely limited by the absence of consciousness. At the same time, semi-altered states of consciousness (Theta) supposedly enable us to induce regenerative processes, while still having a form of

consciousness useful for controlling, directing or observing what's going on in our psyche.

Increased theta frequency has been observed during altered states of consciousness associated with spiritual experiences (Timmermann et al., 2023), including hypnotic states (Jensen, Adachi, & Hakimian, 2015).

This is precisely where meditation comes in, in the following and unfolding of a protocol (called a meditation technique, and varying according to the form of meditation practiced) in a controlled manner but under the influence of an altered state of consciousness tending towards rest or sleep.

The role of the pineal gland in spiritual practices such as meditation would then be the regulation of states of consciousness through the release of hormones linked to sleep and dreaming.

During meditation, the pineal gland is activated by released energy and intrathecal pressure, and the piezoelectric microcalcite crystals produce an electromagnetic field.

6 Conclusion

The pineal gland plays an important role in many cognitive and homeostatic functions, including the regulation of night-time mechanisms, altered states of consciousness and sleep.

The link between the pineal gland and spiritual practices such as meditation lies in the characteristics of the different hormones secreted by this gland. Melatonin and Dimethyltryptamine are both useful when the body shifts from consciousness to a state of unconsciousness, notably sleep. The study of all states of consciousness then becomes the next stage of research, notably states of consciousness that tend towards unconsciousness, or sleep.

Its role in a number of as yet unclear functions, such as hallucinatory mechanisms, dream functioning and the impact of circadian disruption on health, makes this organ particularly interesting to study, and potentially implicated in spiritual practices (including altered states of consciousness) such as meditation.

Based on existing empirical work, this review highlights the various links between the spiritual practice of meditation and the pineal gland and its different functions. This link has been established theoretically since the work of Descartes, and is gradually becoming clearer. In view of the existing literature on the subject, it is difficult to state with any certainty the nature of their relationship. Few studies have measured the impact of this gland's functions on spiritual practices, and vice versa. However, numerous discoveries in these two distinct fields have shed light on their mutual relationship.

In our view, the study of altered states of consciousness and the protocols used in meditation, as well as the observation of their direct benefits, could establish a more certain

relationship between the pineal gland and meditation. It could also contribute to the advancement of a still uncertain field of research.

We suggest that researchers in these fields explore the involvement of the pineal gland in spiritual practices and dream experiences, in order to advance, in our case, the overall understanding of the practice of meditation, which, as we know, has many physical and cognitive benefits. Experimental protocols should be set up to establish links between pineal hormone secretion and meditation-induced benefits.

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